

A new HPLC method for the determination of ciprofloxacin and tinidazole in their pharmaceutical preparations

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Abstract : A new HPLC method for the determination of ciprofloxacin and tinidazole in combination in their pharmaceutical preparations has been described. The method is based on reverse phase liquid chromatography using C-18 column and a suitable mobile phase. The detection is done at 285 nm. The flow rate is adjusted at 2.0 ml/min and linearity is established.

Keywords : Ciprofloxacin, tinidazole.

Ciprofloxacin hydrochloride is chemically 1-cyclopropyl-6-fluoro-1,4-dihydro-4-oxo-7-(1-piperazinyl)-3-quinoline carboxylic acid hydrochloride monohydrate. It has been used as an effective antibacterial agent. Tinidazole is 1-[2-(ethyl sulphonyl)ethyl]-2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole. It is used as an antiprotozoal agent. Determination of ciprofloxacin and tinidazole individually has been reported earlier¹. The present method describes simultaneous determination of two drugs in a single pharmaceutical preparation.

Experimental

Water, acetonitrile, triethylamine (all HPLC grade), orthophosphoric acid (reagent grade), pump, UV detector, recorder (water 746), injector (Rheodyne fix loop 20 μ l) were used for the experiment. Temperature (40 $^{\circ}$ C), wave length (185 nm) and flow rate (2 ml/min) were maintained all through. Mobile phase was made of 2.0 ml H_3PO_4 in 1 L water, pH was maintained (2.1 ± 0.1) with 0.2 M trimethylamine. Experimental mobile phase was prepared by mixing water, acetonitrile and orthophosphoric acid (88 : 12 : 0.176) and filtering through a membrane (0.45 μ m porosity). The solution was degassed as usual.

Procedures :

Accurately weighed 55.50 mg of ciprofloxacin hydrochloride (WS) and 60 mg of tinidazole (WS) were taken in a 100 ml standard volumetric flask. 25 ml of triethylamine was added to it, warmed on water bath, 50 ml of buffer added and stirred well and allowed to cool at room

temperature. Acetonitrile (25 ml) was added to the flask. The solution was diluted with mobile phase to 100 ml and mixed properly and 3 ml of this solution was transferred to a 50 ml standard volumetric flask and diluted with mobile phase to 100 ml and mixed properly. A portion of the solution was filtered through a suitable filter of 0.45 μ m porosity and the filtrate was used as standard preparation. Equal volume (20 μ l) of standard preparations were injected into the chromatograph. The recorded chromatogram and the response of the major peaks were measured. The relative retention time was found to be about 0.37 for tinidazole and 1.0 for ciprofloxacin hydrochloride.

Tablets (20) were weighed and crushed to a fine powder. Powder sample equivalent to 50 mg of ciprofloxacin and 60 mg of tinidazole was weighed accurately and transferred into 100 ml standard volumetric flask, which was then proceeded as per direction for standard preparation.

Relative standard deviation (RSD) is calculated by following equation :

$$\text{Standard deviation } (\sigma) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2}{n-1}}$$

where, \bar{x} = average value, x_i = individual value, n = no. of total measurement.

$$\text{Relative standard deviation (RSD) (\%)} = \frac{100\sigma}{x}$$

Results and discussion

Precision of the method was established by carrying out analysis of analyte ($n = 5$) using the proposed method. The low value of standard deviation shows that the method

deviation for replicate injection was not more than 1.0%. The correlation coefficient (0.999, 0.993), regression coefficient and equation (1.000 , 1.003 and $Y = x + 0.018$, $Y = 1.003x + 0.026$), linear concentration range of (25–500 mcg, 30–600 mcg/ml) of the method are satisfactory for ciprofloxacin and tinidazole respectively.

The above method was validated by published meth-

Table 1. (a) Simultaneous assay of tinidazole and ciprofloxacin in combination

Expt. no.	Batch no.	Tinidazole			Ciprofloxacin		
		Claim per tablet (mg)	Result ^a obtained (%)	Relative standard deviation (%)	Claim per tablet (mg)	Result ^a obtained (%)	Relative standard deviation (%)
1. ^b	NOT-01	600	100.02	0.076	500	100.04	0.013
2. ^b	NOT-02	600	99.38	0.55	500	100.00	0.086
3. ^c	KS-9056	600	99.81	0.36	500	100.16	0.165

(b) Recovery studies

Sl. no.	V	Tinidazole				Ciprofloxacin			
		Amount added (mg)	Amount obtained ^a (mg)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)	Amount added (mg)	Amount obtained ^a (mg)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%)
1.	31.00	30.90	99.69	0.082	24.83	24.94	100.44	0.574	
2.	60.225	60.64	100.68	0.677	50.375	50.495	100.24	0.839	
3.	120.00	120.3	100.25	0.172	100.4	100.0	99.60	0.488	

^aAverage of three determinations.

^bDeys Medical Stores and Mfg. (U.P.) Ltd.

^cCipla Limited.

is precise (Table 1). Accuracy of the method was checked by recovery studies.

Linearity of the method was established by analysis of standard solution containing $1\text{--}5 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and $50\text{--}60 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ for ciprofloxacin and tinidazole respectively. Specificity of the method was established by injecting the placebo of tablet. No interference of the placebo was observed with the principal peak hence the method was specific for these two drugs.

Reggedness of the method was established by carrying out the same experiment on different days, getting the similar analytical data. Robustness of the method was determined by slight change in chromatographic condition, pH (buffer) and temperature modification did not have any significant effect. The detection response was found to be satisfactory for both the drugs at the optimum wavelength of 285 nm. The tailing factor for the analyte peaks was not more than 4.0 and the relative standard

ods² and is fast, selective, precise and reproducible.

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